

Unmanned Aerial Systems in the Russian Arctic: Governance, Infrastructure, and Practical Limits

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Abstract

This article examines the development and application of unmanned aerial systems (UAS) in the Russian Arctic during the period from 2025 to January 2026. It shows that UAS are primarily treated as a practical tool for addressing tasks related to navigation and operational safety along the Northern Sea Route, environmental monitoring, logistics, resource projects, and emergency response in conditions of limited northern infrastructure. The analysis covers institutional and regulatory frameworks, investment and infrastructure solutions, as well as research and development priorities relevant to high-latitude operations. Measurable effects of practical deployment and the growing scale of civilian and state-agency use are identified. At the same time, the study highlights systemic constraints linked to deficiencies in system design, maritime technological bottlenecks, data fragmentation, and a mismatch between the pace of technological development and the availability of supporting infrastructure.

Keywords

Unmanned aerial systems, Russian Arctic, Northern Sea Route, Arctic logistics, operational constraints

Table of Contents

1. Introduction: Use Cases and Operational Drivers	2
2. Governance and Policy Framework for UAS	4
2.1. National Project "Unmanned Aircraft Systems" (2024–2030)	4
2.2. UAS Development Strategy to 2030 with a 2035 Horizon	5
2.3. Federal Russian Economic Forums (2025) as Signals of Arctic UAS Priorities	6
3. Access, Compliance, and Operating Regimes	8
3.1. Standards Roadmap for UAS (2024–2032)	8
3.2. Integrated Airspace Planning System for Manned–Unmanned Operations	8
3.3. Experimental Legal Regimes for UAS Operations	9
3.4. National Drone Adoption Ranking of Regions	10
4. Implementation in the Russian Arctic: Funding, Infrastructure and Operations	12
4.1. Investment and Government Support Measures	12
4.2. Arctic Infrastructure Build-Out (Test Sites, Bases, Mobility)	13
4.3. Measured Operational Outcomes and Civil Uptake	14
4.4. Scale of Civil Adoption	15
5. Technology Priorities for High-Latitude UAS	16
5.1. Arctic-Focused R&D Tracks	16
5.2. Enabling Technologies	17
5.3. Maritime Unmanned Systems and Cross-Domain Integration	19
6. Practical Limits and System Constraints	21
7. Conclusions	23
References	25

1. Introduction: Use Cases and Operational Drivers

Russia treats unmanned aerial systems (UAS) in the Arctic primarily as a practical tool. Their role is defined by the reduction of operational risks, the lowering of infrastructure costs, and the compensation for limitations inherent in satellite-based and crewed assets under northern conditions.

As the Northern Sea Route and the Trans-Arctic Transport Corridor are currently recognized by the Russian leadership as key elements of an integrated Arctic development project of the Russian Federation [1], one of the main directions for UAS use in the region is the provision of navigation and operational safety along the Northern Sea Route. A sustained managerial demand is emerging for civilian UAS as a substitute for, or complement to, helicopters in near-range and beyond-line-of-sight ice reconnaissance [2]. In the most congested sections of the route, satellite data are either insufficiently detailed or unavailable within required time windows, while the use of crewed aviation is costly and operationally constrained. UAS are therefore viewed as a "local layer" of navigational safety with a specific mission profile, including ice reconnaissance at distances of up to approximately 80 nautical miles, loitering times of 7–8 hours, two-way data exchange with a carrier vessel, and minimal requirements for icebreaker modification [2]. This logic is already being secured through regional pilot projects and regulatory planning documents related to the Northern Sea Route [3], [4].

A second important direction is local-scale mapping and the updating of ground reality. In hard-to-reach Arctic settlements and coastal infrastructure zones, UAS are used to refine and correct cartographic baselines, as satellite remote sensing data with resolutions of around 30 m per pixel are considered insufficient for managerial and engineering decisions. UAS-based aerial surveys are directly integrated into decision-making processes, ranging from the justification of coastal protection measures to subsequent assessments of infrastructure project performance. A key effect is the revision of official assumptions regarding baseline territorial conditions, as UAS enable the identification of previously undocumented anthropogenic impacts [5].

A third key direction concerns environmental safety and emergency response, particularly in the oil and gas sector. UAS are being institutionally incorporated into oil spill response: whereas unmanned aviation was previously not used for dispersant application or the active phase of spill mitigation, since late 2025 it has been considered a standard element, alongside satellite monitoring and shore-based data analysis centers [6]. In a broader sense, UAS enhance continuous environmental monitoring of Arctic seas and coastal areas, reducing the risk of delayed detection of environmental damage.

Logistical support for Arctic resource projects represents another important area of application. In the oil, gas, and mining sectors, UAS—often in combination with ground and underwater unmanned systems—are already used for cargo delivery, environmental monitoring, seismic and geological surveys, mapping, laser scanning, and infrastructure inspection [7]. Over a longer-term horizon, the results of civilian UAS operations are directly linked to increases in identified reserves of strategic resources, including uranium, manganese, chromium, and titanium [8].

This set of use cases corresponds to the functional model of unmanned technology application in Arctic energy projects described in the academic literature. In this model, unmanned systems are treated not as experimental solutions but as operational instruments integrated into routine production and support activities, rather than limited to isolated pilot deployments [49].

Logistics and supply for Arctic settlements constitute a further task. Russia sees potential in developing Arctic logistics chains using heavy-lift UAS, including cargo delivery to remote settlements, servicing of extraction sites, and monitoring of power lines and pipelines [6]. Heavy-lift UAS are viewed as an element of aerial logistics that complements the Northern Sea Route and reduces the dependence of northern regions on seasonal delivery windows.

Finally, UAS are being integrated into the Arctic security and emergency response system. The development of computer vision, GNSS-independent navigation, and search-and-rescue scenarios is explicitly oriented toward northern conditions, including locating people in hard-to-reach terrain, operating in extreme weather, and supporting expeditionary and emergency missions [9]. The involvement of the Ministry of Emergency Situations and the Ministry of Internal Affairs indicates that this is not an experimental domain, but the incorporation of unmanned systems into the standard security architecture of the Arctic.

2. Governance and Policy Framework for UAS

At present, Russia is forming a centralized system for governing the development and deployment of unmanned aerial systems (UAS), bringing together industrial policy, aviation regulation, and security regimes.

The Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Russian Federation acts as the key sectoral coordinator, overseeing the national project "Unmanned Aircraft Systems," the UAS Development Strategy to 2030 with a 2035 horizon, and the system of support measures for domestic manufacturers.

Regulation is structured according to the principle of "from use cases to technologies." Priority is given to certification, the integration of UAS into unified airspace, localization of production, and demand creation through state and quasi-state procurement. Control over drone operations has been strengthened through the introduction of unified identification systems and digital platforms for flight coordination and monitoring [9].

The architecture of federal projects forms a continuous governance chain—"development → access → market → scaling." In the Arctic context, this implies the absence of a dedicated Arctic-specific project and a reliance on integrating the objectives of Arctic Zone development into general technological scenarios applicable nationwide. The establishment of a unified certification system and operational infrastructure creates organizational conditions for the regular and scalable use of UAS across different scenarios in northern regions, reducing reliance on crewed aviation in hard-to-reach areas.

In early 2026, the relevance of tasks related to the development of Russian autonomous and unmanned systems was reaffirmed at the highest political level [10]. At the presidential level, the objective was articulated to move from experimental regimes to mass deployment, to improve sectoral governance through coordination among ministries, regions, business, and the research community, and to ensure conditions for serial production and the formation of a unified technological base. Particular emphasis was placed on the role of domestically developed algorithms and artificial intelligence solutions for UAS.

It was also proposed to extend experimental regimes for UAS development to the Far East, with the accumulated experience subsequently expected to be transferred and applied to Arctic regions of Russia.

2.1. National Project "Unmanned Aircraft Systems" (2024–2030)

The national project "Unmanned Aircraft Systems" has been implemented in Russia at the federal level since 2024.

Structurally, the project covers the full life cycle of UAS, including the development and serial production of unmanned aircraft and components, the creation of specialized infrastructure (droneports, test ranges, control and surveillance systems), workforce training, certification and regulatory support, as well as support for applied and advanced research and development. Project financing provides for multi-billion annual allocations from the federal budget through 2030, including dedicated competitive mechanisms to support UAS developers and manufacturers.

From the outset, implementation of the national project has been oriented toward nationwide scaling rather than being limited to pilot regions. At the same time, the Far East and northern territories are used as zones for accelerated testing and rollout.

The project is directly linked to objectives of technological sovereignty and Russia's long-term socio-economic development strategy through 2030–2035, and is treated as a fundamental technological priority capable of increasing efficiency in core sectors of the economy, reducing costs, and creating new markets [11].

In line with the project's targets, Russia aims to enter the group of global leaders in drone production and use by 2030, and by 2035 to transform unmanned technologies into one of the system-forming drivers of economic development [9].

The national project relies on a model of accelerated development for eastern and northern territories. The Far East is positioned as a strategic platform for UAS scaling: Sakhalin Oblast, where Russia's first droneport "Pushistyy" has been established, is used as a site for testing serial production, operational deployment, and the integration of unmanned systems into economic activity. By presidential instruction, this experience is to be extended to the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation, explicitly linking UAS development to the Arctic and northern agenda.

According to the Ministry of Transport, Russia has already established a "comprehensive legal foundation" for UAS covering the entire life cycle of unmanned systems, and in a number of regulatory parameters Russia is assessed as being ahead of the United States and China [12]. At present, 21 UAS manufacturing companies operate in the Far East, some of them residents of advanced development territories and the Free Port of Vladivostok. The region is used as a platform for serial production, testing, and operational integration of unmanned systems into economic processes, with subsequent scaling of solutions to other regions of the country, including the Arctic [11]. Although the Arctic is not formally designated as a separate section within the national project, the development of civilian UAS is implicitly envisaged with due regard to the harsh conditions of the North.

2.2. UAS Development Strategy to 2030 with a 2035 Horizon

The Development Strategy for Unmanned Aviation of the Russian Federation through 2030, with a horizon to 2035, formalizes a revision of the core priorities of state policy in the UAS domain and sets an updated trajectory for sectoral development. In autumn 2025, the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia presented a draft of the new strategy intended to replace the 2023 version and to recalibrate expectations regarding market dynamics and the production of unmanned aerial systems [13], [14].

The key change introduced by the strategy consists in moderating growth forecasts for the sector through 2030 while simultaneously shifting the emphasis toward accelerated and large-scale expansion in the period 2031–2035. According to the draft, the cumulative domestic UAS market volume in 2023–2026 is estimated at 399 thousand units under the baseline scenario and 419 thousand units under the progressive scenario. For 2027–2030, the forecast has been revised downward compared to the current strategy, to 631–663 thousand units versus the previously projected 684–719 thousand units. By contrast, for the 2031–2035 horizon the strategy envisages a sharp increase in market volume to 1.47–1.55 million units, substantially exceeding the estimates of the previous version of the document.

A similar logic is embedded in production forecasts for unmanned aerial systems. Output in 2023–2026 is projected at 45.4–47.7 thousand units (compared to 52.1–55.4 thousand units in the existing strategy), and at 93.4–98 thousand units in 2027–2030 (versus 105.5–116.8 thousand units). In the period 2031–2035 the strategy provides for production of 228.5–240 thousand UAS, reflecting the transition of the sector to a mature development phase after 2030 and a strategic focus on scaling serial production

From the perspective of structural targets, the strategy sets the objective of achieving a 70.3% share of domestically produced unmanned systems in the Russian market by 2030 and an 80% share in the government procurement segment, as well as a sectoral technological independence level of 81.1%. The document identifies agriculture, logistics, infrastructure monitoring, and the updating of geospatial data as priority application areas for UAS [14].

Overall, the updated strategy reflects a shift from rapid indicator growth in the short term toward a more cautious development phase through 2030, followed by a large-scale expansion in 2031–2035. Within this logic, unmanned aviation is treated as a sector moving from an initial formation stage toward becoming a system-forming element of the economy, which institutionally complements the national project "Unmanned Aircraft Systems" and establishes a long-term state policy framework for UAS development.

2.3. Federal Russian Economic Forums (2025) as Signals of Arctic UAS Priorities

At major Russian economic forums in 2025, where Arctic issues occupied a visible place on the agenda, the development of unmanned aerial systems (UAS) was interpreted in a non-uniform manner.

At the St. Petersburg International Economic Forum in 2025, the development of unmanned aerial systems was not presented as an independent direction of economic policy. References to unmanned technologies were fragmentary and forward-looking in nature. In particular, the Special Representative of the President of the Russian Federation for Digital and Technological Development, Dmitry Peskov, noted that the rapid development of drones and their potential role in logistics could, in the future, elevate the "drone economy" to one of the central themes of subsequent forums, while emphasizing that this referred to a prospective stage rather than the current SPIEF agenda [15].

A different logic was observed at the Eastern Economic Forum in 2025. Here, UAS were embedded within the institutional framework of spatial development, primarily with respect to the Far East and the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation. A key emphasis was placed on Sakhalin and the Kuril Islands as a model territory for deploying unmanned solutions under conditions of complex terrain, remoteness, and limited conventional infrastructure. The President of Russia identified this region as a base platform for testing unmanned technologies with subsequent dissemination of accumulated experience to other regions of the Far Eastern Federal District, while the Ministry for the Development of the Far East and the Arctic formalized the Sakhalin experiment as a reference model for regional replication [16].

In a broader context, EEF-2025 served as a venue for articulating macro-regional priorities, within which a federal signal was formulated regarding the need for active deployment of unmanned technologies in both the Far Eastern and Arctic macro-regions. UAS were directly linked to tasks of logistics, transport accessibility, and cost reduction in the development of remote territories [7]. For the first time, an explicit need was articulated for a unified preferential regime for businesses employing unmanned technologies in these regions,

indicating a shift in emphasis from experimental use toward instruments of economic and infrastructure policy.

Within the established state policy framework, particular importance is therefore attached to the analysis of concrete mechanisms of access, regulation, and operation through which declared UAS development priorities are implemented in practice. It is this instrumental level that defines the permissible scales, regimes, and scenarios for the use of unmanned aerial systems, including under Arctic conditions.

3. Access, Compliance, and Operating Regimes

While state policy sets the general directions for UAS development, regulatory and institutional access mechanisms define the practical limits of their use. It is these mechanisms that determine the regimes, scales, and operational scenarios under which unmanned aerial systems can be used on a regular basis. For Arctic territories, the role of access mechanisms becomes particularly pronounced, as standard aviation regulations and infrastructure conditions often prove either inapplicable or economically inefficient. This section examines the key instruments through which Russia is transitioning from experimental UAS use to systematic operation.

3.1. Standards Roadmap for UAS (2024–2032)

The prospective standardization program for unmanned aerial systems for the period 2024–2032 is an active departmental regulatory and planning document developed within the Rosstandart system, in cooperation with the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia [17]. It defines the scope, sequencing, and priorities for the development of national standards across the entire UAS ecosystem, ranging from aircraft and components to ground infrastructure and operational processes.

Although the program does not include a dedicated "Arctic" section, it is in practice oriented toward conditions characteristic of the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation, through specific groups of technical and operational requirements.

In particular, the program provides for the development of standards governing the testing and operation of UAS under low and extremely low temperature conditions, including methods for assessing flight performance, reliability, and system stability in cold environments.

In addition, the program standardizes types of work and operations typical of remote and hard-to-reach territories, such as monitoring of extended objects, data collection and transmission, aerial operations, and cargo transport, including operations conducted outside populated areas. In 2026, within the jointly approved UAS standardization program for 2024–2032, the development of new national standards (GOST) for unmanned aerial system components is underway. At present, more than 15 standards are already in force in the field of unmanned aviation in Russia, confirming that the program has entered the phase of practical implementation [18].

3.2. Integrated Airspace Planning System for Manned–Unmanned Operations

The Unified Integrated Airspace Use Planning System (ES OrVD) is a digital infrastructure system designed for the joint planning, coordination, and control of flights by crewed and unmanned aircraft within the unified airspace of the Russian Federation [19].

In architectural terms, ES OrVD is conceived as a centralized platform that integrates previously fragmented elements, including the system for submitting and processing flight plans, centralized airspace-use databases, surveillance and identification tools for airborne objects, and services for dispatching and automated planning. The system's core task is to ensure conflict-free planning of joint operations by crewed and unmanned aviation, based on a unified data set and standardized safety procedures.

From the perspective of unmanned aerial systems, ES OrVD performs the function of infrastructural access to the unified airspace. Drone operations are shifted from a regime of

individual permits and temporary exemptions to a mode of systematic planning comparable to that applied to crewed aviation. This implies mandatory operational visibility of UAS for air traffic controllers and pilots, integration of navigation and surveillance data, and the possibility of automated scaling of operations beyond local pilot zones.

Practical implementation of the system is structured in stages. The first stage covers the period 2025–2027 and provides for the creation of a basic version of EIS PIVP, linked to the centralized ES OrVD database, including the testing of safety procedures and integration with existing air traffic management systems [20]. Funding for the first stage has been approved at approximately 10.4 billion rubles, reflecting the scale of the task of building a federal-level supra-system rather than a localized IT solution. The second stage (2028–2030) envisages expanded functionality and system-wide scaling.

It is fundamentally important that ES OrVD is not designed as a system "for drones only." It is intended to integrate crewed and unmanned aviation within a single management framework, including the alignment of heterogeneous databases, regulatory regimes, and technical protocols.

As of the period from November 2025 to early February 2026, no public information has been released regarding system launch, pilot operation, or practical results of ES OrVD. This indicates that the project has entered a non-public phase of contracting, system design, and interagency coordination typical of large-scale infrastructure initiatives, and does not suggest project discontinuation.

In the context of UAS development in Russia, including the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation, ES OrVD represents one of the key systemic frameworks defining the permissible scale and forms of unmanned aviation use and establishing institutional conditions for its transition to regular operation.

3.3. Experimental Legal Regimes for UAS Operations

The experimental legal regime (ELR) for digital innovations in unmanned aerial systems operation serves in Russia as a core instrument for the practical deployment of UAS where standard aviation regulations are difficult to apply or economically inefficient, primarily in northern and Arctic regions.

The regime was introduced by a Government of the Russian Federation decree dated 22 March 2022 and initially covered Kamchatka Krai, Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug–Yugra, Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, and Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug. In 2025, its validity was extended until 2028, with adjustments to the regime's parameters [21]. This extension confirmed sustained demand for the ELR as an operational mechanism for UAS use, particularly in KhMAO–Yugra and YaNAO, where drones are employed for monitoring, logistics, and aerial operations under conditions of sparse infrastructure and complex geography.

By the end of 2025, a shift in the ELR from a territorial to a functional logic was observed. The Ministry of Economic Development of Russia announced preparations for a separate experimental legal regime for the Northern Sea Route, focused on the use of shipborne UAS for ice reconnaissance, as well as cargo delivery and aerial operations [4]. Submission of the draft to the government was scheduled for January 2026, with the regime expected to be established in the first quarter of 2026.

In parallel, information appeared on the development of an ELR involving UAS operations in Tomsk Oblast, where cargo transport and aerial tasks are also planned. This points to an expansion of experimental geography beyond the Arctic, while preserving a focus on remote and weakly infrastructured territories.

Overall, the ELR for UAS has evolved from a set of limited regional pilots into a systemic regulatory mechanism that is gradually specializing by function—such as ice reconnaissance, logistics, and aerial operations—and scaling across key transport and resource domains of the country, including the Arctic Zone and the Northern Sea Route.

3.4. National Drone Adoption Ranking of Regions

The National Drone Adoption Ranking (regional drone adoption index) was conducted in 2025 as the first federal instrument for assessing the actual level of regional engagement in the development of the unmanned aviation sector in Russia [22]. Its purpose was to capture not declarative plans but concrete regional efforts to deploy unmanned aerial systems, and to use the results for the allocation of state support measures. Regions demonstrating the strongest performance were treated as priority recipients of benefits and subsidies.

The ranking was constructed as an assessment of regional activity in UAS sector development, while accounting for objective constraints, including existing restrictions and airspace-use regimes. Regional performance was evaluated against a set of criteria, such as the number of UAS in operation, the availability of regional incentives for market participants, and the functioning of experimental legal regimes permitting UAS flights. Particular emphasis was placed on identifying the most in-demand application scenarios, including emergency response and rescue operations, as well as on laying the groundwork for a national system of statistics on unmanned flights.

The first iteration of the ranking had a limited, pilot character. Forty-seven regions participated, meaning that not all constituent entities of the Russian Federation were covered, and the results were not formalized as final or legally binding. The outcomes were treated primarily as an analytical tool: they helped to identify gaps in regulation, financing, and infrastructure, and to improve coordination between regional authorities, UAS operators, and customers. In addition, the ranking was used to identify areas where stronger federal-level involvement was required, particularly in regulatory and financial support.

In 2025, the ranking was embedded into the broader federal framework for unmanned aviation development. From 2026 onward, participation in the National Drone Adoption Ranking becomes mandatory for all regions of the Russian Federation [3]. The ranking was linked to infrastructure and territorial policy: in the same year, presidential instructions were issued to explore the creation of UAS landing sites in Arctic regions, reinforcing the role of the ranking as a tool for selecting territories for priority development of unmanned infrastructure in remote and northern areas [23].

As of December 2025–February 2026, no substantive public updates on the National Drone Adoption Ranking had been recorded. No new results, score recalculations, expanded regional lists, updated evaluation methodologies, or regulatory acts detailing the mechanism for mandatory regional participation from 2026 were published.

The access mechanisms reviewed above form a multi-layered and not yet fully synchronized system governing the use of UAS. The standards roadmap, the integrated airspace planning system, experimental legal regimes, and the regional ranking address different tasks but

collectively define the institutional boundaries for scaling unmanned aviation. For the Arctic, these instruments create conditions for moving from fragmented pilot projects to regular use, while at the same time maintaining dependence on experimental regimes and administrative decisions. Under these conditions, the key issue becomes how institutional access frameworks are translated into investment decisions, infrastructure projects, and a sustainable practice of UAS operation, including in Arctic regions.

4. Implementation in the Russian Arctic: Funding, Infrastructure and Operations

The transition from regulatory mechanisms to the practical operation of unmanned aerial systems in the Arctic is manifested through investment decisions, infrastructure development, and the accumulation of operational experience. It is at this level that it becomes possible to assess the extent to which institutional arrangements are translated into stable operational chains. In this context, investments, infrastructure, and practice are treated as instruments for implementing declared UAS use scenarios, within which both achieved effects and persistent structural constraints become evident. This section focuses on the analysis of concrete mechanisms and organizational forms through which these processes are realized.

4.1. Investment and Government Support Measures

By 2026, Russia has formed a system of investment and state support in the unmanned aviation sector that covers flight management infrastructure, regional pilot projects, and incentives for domestic UAS manufacturing.

A reference regional example is Sakhalin Oblast, where the droneport "Pushisty" is positioned as the first specialized unmanned infrastructure facility in Russia. Sakhalin has been designated as a pilot territory, whose solutions are intended for replication in other regions, with relevant federal authorities confirming their readiness to provide federal-level support for the project.

The core volume of investment is concentrated at the federal level, primarily in the development of infrastructure for managing unmanned flights. In 2025, the State Corporation for Air Traffic Management allocated 10.26 billion rubles to the development of specialized UAS flight management infrastructure. Of this amount, 5.75 billion rubles were earmarked for equipment procurement and 4.5 billion rubles for software development and commissioning works. The contractor for this project is the Almaz-Antey concern, with completion scheduled by the end of 2027. These investments are directly linked to the formation of the Unified Integrated Airspace Use Planning System (ES OrVD). In a broader horizon, total funding for UAS flight infrastructure in Russia through 2030 is estimated at 236 billion rubles, with the most capital-intensive component remaining the deployment of a unified command-and-control line infrastructure [24].

In parallel, a framework of tax and financial support for UAS manufacturers is being developed. In August 2025, the State Duma adopted at first reading a bill introducing a zero VAT rate on the sale of civilian drones with a mass between 0.15 and 30 kg, as well as on systems produced within the Eurasian Economic Union. The bill also provides for the elimination of VAT on imported components (engines, spare parts, and other components) used in the production, repair, and modernization of drones, and extends these benefits to prototypes and elements used in development and testing. The measures are set to remain in effect until 31 December 2027, after which their effectiveness is to be assessed. These decisions are linked to Russia's strategy of achieving technological leadership in the unmanned sector by 2030 [25].

In addition, a set of direct state support measures is in place, including grants of up to 100 million rubles, subsidies for certification, compensation of R&D costs, and sales-stimulation mechanisms through discounts [11]. These instruments are aimed at accelerating serial production and lowering barriers to market entry for domestically produced UAS.

Taken together, investments in infrastructure, tax incentives, and targeted support for developers form a multi-level model of UAS sector development, in which federal flight management systems are combined with regional pilot projects and economic incentives for manufacturers.

4.2. Arctic Infrastructure Build-Out (Test Sites, Bases, Mobility)

In 2024–2025, a cluster of testing and operational infrastructure for unmanned aerial systems began to take shape in the Russian Arctic and adjacent northern regions. This infrastructure is oriented toward operation under extreme climatic conditions and toward the subsequent scaling of Arctic UAS use scenarios.

A key scientific and production element of this system is the Polar Center under development in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia). More than 550 million rubles have been allocated from the federal budget for its development. The center is being established as part of the Yakutia technopark and is intended for the production and testing of unmanned aircraft capable of operating at temperatures down to -60 °C. It is positioned simultaneously as a production site, a testing range, and an environment for startups and industry residents. The center focuses on the development of frost-resistant components, software, and new materials, while Yakutia itself is treated as a natural environment for the verification of Arctic technologies. In the longer term, this ecosystem is expected to include the use of unmanned airships with payload capacities of up to one metric ton, highlighting the infrastructure's orientation toward logistics, medical support, and emergency response tasks in the Arctic [26].

In parallel, basing and operational infrastructure for UAS is being developed in the Far Eastern macro-region. On Sakhalin, the "Pushistyy" droneport is being expanded and is regarded as the first specialized facility of this type in Russia, as well as a model for subsequent replication. Official materials record plans to create similar droneports in the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation, indicating an intention to form a networked basing infrastructure for unmanned systems across northern regions [11].

The most operationally mature facility to date has been created in the Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug. In the regional capital, an Arctic Testing Center has been opened, becoming the first site in Russia where crewed and unmanned aircraft are co-located. The center's infrastructure includes two complementary sites. The stationary "Obdorsk" site is equipped with modular buildings for UAS and specialized equipment, an apron with a taxiway, and a landing area. The second site is mobile and is based on two "Burlak" all-terrain vehicles fitted with equipment for unmanned flights, allowing it to be rapidly deployed in any area and adapted to specific operational tasks. It is noted that the facility was created within six months, and its infrastructure is planned for future use in forming a flexible UAS route network in the Arctic [27].

In addition, existing aerodrome infrastructure is being adapted for unmanned logistics in the Arctic. In 2025, plans were announced to modernize aerodromes in the Komi Republic to accommodate cargo UAS designed for Arctic operating conditions [23]. The new infrastructure is intended to support cargo delivery to hard-to-reach and isolated settlements, including territories separated by water barriers, underscoring a shift toward integrating UAS into the regular transport system of the North.

Taken together, these elements reflect a transition from fragmented pilot testing toward the formation of supporting UAS infrastructure in the Arctic, encompassing scientific and production centers, stationary and mobile test sites, and basing facilities. This infrastructure is

developing not as a single centralized project, but as a network of regional nodes oriented toward different aspects of Arctic application, ranging from testing and R&D to operation and the construction of route networks.

4.3. Measured Operational Outcomes and Civil Uptake

The application of unmanned aerial systems in the Arctic is already delivering measurable practical results, confirming their economic, managerial, and institutional viability.

One of the most indicative effects is the contribution of UAS to the expansion of the resource base. As of January 2026, seven potential mineral deposits in the Far East and Siberia had been identified with the use of unmanned aerial systems [8]. This result demonstrates the practical effectiveness of UAS as a tool for primary exploration and for refining geological anomalies in hard-to-reach areas, where traditional methods are either prohibitively costly or constrained by seasonality. In addition, it has been documented that in the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation UAS are used as the primary instrument for field monitoring of cryogenic processes: since 2018, all quantitative data on the dynamics of thermokarst features in Central Yamal for the period 2019–2025 have been obtained through high-resolution UAS-based aerial surveys, enabling regular observation of growth, stabilization, or overgrowth of specific landforms [28].

A second key outcome is the economic effect of unmanned logistics and monitoring in Arctic and sub-Arctic projects. According to expert assessments, the introduction of unmanned logistics solutions in the Far East and the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation can reduce the cost of energy projects by up to 38% and accelerate their implementation by approximately 24% [7]. These effects are partly explained by the ability of unmanned systems to operate on a continuous, round-the-clock basis under harsh Arctic conditions, reducing downtime and mitigating risks associated with human presence [49]. The resulting cost reductions are primarily linked to lower reliance on crewed aviation and reduced weather- and infrastructure-related losses. Departmental practice further reinforces this picture: the existence of an in-house fleet of unmanned aerial vehicles within the Marine Rescue Service enables rapid detection of pollution in Arctic waters and immediate initiation of oil spill response measures without reliance on external operators [6]. The academic literature notes that such estimates are typically derived from aggregated corporate reporting and case-based assessments, and should therefore be interpreted as indicative rather than universal benchmarks [49].

In practical terms, unmanned systems already perform a broad range of functions at Arctic oil and gas fields, including cargo delivery, environmental monitoring, seismic surveys, and photo and video documentation [29]. A particularly important result is not merely the expansion of functional scope, but the operational resilience of these activities: UAS demonstrate the ability to operate around the clock under low temperatures, strong winds, and ice conditions, which substantially enhances the reliability of production cycles in the Arctic. Comparable operational robustness has also been recorded in emergency response systems, where UAS are employed by units of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of Russia during firefighting and rescue operations, including situations that pose heightened risks to personnel safety, reflecting documented departmental experience with UAS operation in cold regions [30].

A separate applied dimension relates to ensuring the safety and manageability of the Northern Sea Route. In academic studies, UAS are consistently treated as an element of the NSR management system for ice reconnaissance, route optimization, reduction of vessel escort times, and enhancement of overall transport safety [31]. The economic efficiency of UAS use compared to helicopters has been demonstrated, including when based on nuclear icebreakers,

as well as their role in building the digital and environmental infrastructure of the Northern Sea Route through continuous collection of ice and meteorological data.

Taken together, these findings indicate that UAS in the Arctic have already moved beyond the category of prospective technologies and entered the category of tools with demonstrated impact across resource exploration, monitoring of natural processes, logistics, environmental safety, and the management of critical infrastructure.

4.4. Scale of Civil Adoption

The actual level of civilian UAS adoption in Russia is confirmed by the existence of dedicated departmental fleets. As of January 2026, the Ministry of Natural Resources of the Russian Federation operated 1,626 unmanned aerial vehicles, used for environmental monitoring, observation of natural sites, and tasks related to environmental protection [8].

Similarly, the Marine Rescue Service maintains its own UAS fleet, enabling the rapid detection of marine pollution and the immediate initiation of oil spill response measures without reliance on external operators, thereby increasing operational autonomy and response speed [6]. The size of the Marine Rescue Service fleet is not publicly disclosed, reflecting the fragmented nature of available federal-level statistics on civilian UAS.

An assessment of investment flows, infrastructure solutions, and applied practice indicates that UAS development in the Russian Arctic is already producing measurable results. A network of testing and operational sites is being formed, substantial infrastructure investments are being implemented, and unmanned systems are beginning to perform regular functions in logistics, monitoring, and security provision. The presence of investment and infrastructure does not automatically eliminate operational and technological constraints and, in some cases, brings them into sharper relief. Under these conditions, further scaling of UAS use is determined less by the expansion of investment programs than by advances in technological solutions capable of addressing the identified constraints.

5. Technology Priorities for High-Latitude UAS

Technological development of unmanned aerial systems in the period under review is largely driven by the need to adapt UAS to the specific conditions of Arctic operation. Research and development and the deployment of new technologies are not treated in isolation, but as responses to identified constraints related to infrastructure, connectivity, energy supply, and autonomy requirements in high-latitude environments. Within this logic, technological solutions are oriented toward ensuring stable and regular UAS operation in northern regions, rather than toward experimental demonstration of individual capabilities. This section analyzes the key directions of technological development relevant to the application of unmanned aerial systems in the Arctic.

5.1. Arctic-Focused R&D Tracks

In 2024–2025, a targeted intensification of R&D on unmanned aerial systems was recorded in Russia, within which Arctic conditions are treated not as a peripheral case but as a baseline scenario for validating technological solutions. This is reflected both in the demonstration of specific platforms and in the formation of cross-cutting technological tracks oriented toward operation in high latitudes [9].

At a systemic level, R&D efforts are structured around several key technological areas critical for Arctic operation. These include autonomy and navigation in the absence of reliable GNSS coverage, long-range and resilient communications, power and propulsion systems, and resistance to cold, wind, icing, and abrasive environments. Particular attention is given to the development of hybrid and vertical take-off configurations, swarm and group UAS systems, as well as onboard computing and local AI, enabling decision-making under conditions of lost connectivity and limited maintenance.

Within these tracks, an applied line of autonomous monitoring of Arctic infrastructure based on UAS is being developed. In 2025, an Arctic-capable UAS complex was presented, comprising an unmanned aircraft with a mass of up to 30 kg, a droneport, and a neural-network-based data processing system. The complex is designed for operation at temperatures down to -40°C , humidity levels of up to 90%, and strong winds, with a flight range exceeding 170 km. A tenfold reduction in manual labor requirements and a reduction in monitoring costs to 200–300 rubles per kilometer ($\approx 2\text{--}3$ euros per kilometer) were reported, making such solutions potentially applicable in the oil and gas sector, energy, telecommunications, and industrial operations in Arctic areas [32].

In parallel, universal and "northern" solutions are being developed in Russian practice to test key technological and operational approaches. These systems have not yet been deployed in the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation and are not positioned as specialized Arctic UAS; however, they form a technological reserve from which solutions can subsequently be adapted to more severe operating conditions, including those of the Arctic.

For example, the universal UAS "Brazhnik," developed and tested on Sakhalin, demonstrated multifunctionality, high resistance to interference, and robustness against external impacts. The platform is capable of carrying payloads of up to 10 kg, including gas analyzers, laser scanners, thermal imagers, and relay equipment, with an endurance of up to 60 minutes, and is equipped with the domestically developed secure communications system "Hermes" [33]. In 2025, the "Brazhnik" system was publicly presented at specialized technology events [16].

At the same time, the segment of long-range and interregional flights is developing. The unmanned aircraft "Aist" ("Aurora-UAS") was presented, having previously completed a flight under standard aviation rules between Okha and Nikolayevsk-on-Amur, and preparations were announced for a flight to the Southern Kuril Islands [11]. Operational practice in this segment is being shaped by the airline Aurora-UAS, which has obtained official status as a UAS operator and already performs monitoring, aerial surveying, forest protection, and testing of interregional cargo flights with payloads of several hundred kilograms.

An important element of this agenda is the institutional linkage of R&D with real northern routes and infrastructure. The technological competition "Aerologistics 2.0" is creating a foundation for the use of civilian UAS in the Arctic as an autonomous logistics instrument, oriented toward extreme meteorological conditions and minimal operator involvement. The coupling of trials to northern test sites and existing crewed aviation routes indicates an effort to integrate R&D outcomes into the functioning transport system, rather than to limit activity to laboratory or demonstrative settings.

A key scientific and production element of this system is the Polar Center under development in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia). More than 550 million rubles (≈ 5.5 million euros) have been allocated from the federal budget for its development. The center is being established as part of the Yakutia technopark and is intended for the production and testing of unmanned aircraft capable of operating at temperatures down to -60 °C. It is positioned simultaneously as a production site, a testing range, and an environment for startups and industry residents. The center focuses on the development of frost-resistant components, software, and new materials, while Yakutia itself is treated as a natural environment for the verification of Arctic technologies. In the longer term, this ecosystem is expected to include the use of unmanned airships with payload capacities of up to one metric ton, highlighting the infrastructure's orientation toward logistics, medical support, and emergency response tasks in the Arctic [26].

5.2. Enabling Technologies

In 2024–2025, Russia recorded a shift from isolated engineering solutions toward integrated technology packages aimed at removing key constraints on UAS use in the Arctic—connectivity, energy supply, autonomy, and operational safety.

One of the most illustrative directions is the so-called "dome communication" concept between unmanned aerial systems. In 2025, a practical implementation of this concept was successfully demonstrated: a UAS operated by Geoscan and equipped with a radio complex of the Gonets satellite system was lifted to an altitude of 4 km, providing stable communications coverage over an area with a diameter of approximately 340 km. Within this zone, reliable connectivity was ensured for ground users, vehicles, and other low-altitude unmanned platforms [34]. The technology is viewed as an alternative to cost-intensive ground-based communications infrastructure and has direct applied value for the Arctic, including support for expeditions, remote settlements, and vessels operating along the Northern Sea Route.

An orbital-level extension of this approach is the highly elliptical satellite system "Express-RV," designed to provide continuous UAS connectivity in the Arctic. The launch of the first satellites is scheduled for late 2026, and the spacecraft are already in the manufacturing stage, which is expected to expand the operational capabilities of unmanned systems in high latitudes [35].

In parallel, integrated systems for autonomous infrastructure monitoring are being developed for operation under Arctic climatic conditions. In 2025, a system was presented comprising a

UAS with a mass of up to 30 kg, a droneport, and a neural-network-based data analysis system. The solution is designed for operation at temperatures down to $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, humidity levels of up to 90%, and strong winds, with a flight range exceeding 170 km, and is reported to reduce manual labor requirements by a factor of ten [36]. The system is targeted at the oil and gas sector, energy, communications, utilities, and industrial facilities, and demonstrates a transition from fragmented flights to fully automated monitoring.

Further development of this logic includes the creation of UAS equipped with integrated seismic sensors and ground-penetration mechanisms intended for autonomous seismic exploration in hard-to-reach areas, including the Arctic and ice-covered terrains [37]. Sensor integration into the drone, autonomous selection of measurement points, and subsequent recovery of the platform reduce logistical and infrastructure costs and extend UAS functionality from observation to active geophysical measurement.

A separate technological direction concerns cargo UAS. Russian developers have produced the heavy unmanned platform "Koshchey," designed to carry payloads exceeding 300 kg, as well as an octocopter developed by the company Aviron with a payload capacity ranging from 50 to 320 kg. The platform has a cruising speed of approximately 80 km/h, a distributed power supply system, and retains controllability in the event of partial engine failure, enabling emergency landing at distances of 35–40 km [36]. The use of a proprietary secure communications system and production localization at a level of around 80% underscore the project's orientation toward serial deployment in hard-to-reach areas.

Energy supply remains a critical technological bottleneck for Arctic operations, and in 2025 specialized power solutions for northern-class unmanned platforms were presented. United Engine Corporation developed a turbogenerator based on the VK-650V engine with an output of 400 kW and a mass of 200 kg, as well as the EU-35 power unit with an output of 35 kW and a mass of 105 kg, intended for heavy UAS and vertical or ultra-short take-off and landing platforms [38]. These solutions are designed to ensure autonomous power supply under extreme climatic conditions and directly address the problem of battery degradation in cold environments.

Finally, a distinct class of technologies is aimed at improving the safety and reliability of battery systems. In 2025, engineering solutions for thermal protection and fire safety of lithium-ion batteries were presented. A gel-based heat-retention material developed at SUAI allows batteries to remain operational at temperatures down to $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while a fire-retardant coating proposed at NUST MISIS increases battery thermal resistance to 300–400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, reducing the risk of thermal runaway and accidents in autonomous operating modes [39].

An additional institutional-technological element is the development of a unified UAS identification and online monitoring system based on the ERA-GLONASS platform [11]. This system ensures transparency of data on flights and operators and is viewed as a precondition for easing regulatory restrictions and opening airspace for unmanned operations, including in northern regions.

Overall, new UAS technologies for Arctic applications in Russia are focused not on individual platforms, but on the formation of an integrated system—communications, energy supply, autonomous measurement capabilities, cold-weather protection, and institutional access—without which large-scale and regular unmanned operations in high latitudes remain unattainable.

5.3. Maritime Unmanned Systems and Cross-Domain Integration

In 2025–2026, the development of maritime unmanned systems in the Russian Arctic entered a phase of practical activation, characterized by the launch of regional pilot projects, an expanding range of technical solutions, and initial steps toward regulatory and industrial support. The focus shifted toward testing concrete operational scenarios in northern waters, including cargo logistics, monitoring, and search-and-rescue operations. In parallel, an applied line of integration between maritime unmanned platforms and aerial UAS began to take shape, reflecting a transition from isolated pilots to cross-domain use of unmanned systems.

In Arctic offshore energy projects, unmanned technologies are also applied in the form of seabed and underwater systems used for seismic surveys and marine geological exploration. Academic studies describe the deployment of autonomous seabed stations for Arctic shelf research as a mature applied solution integrated into industrial survey workflows, including cases of domestically developed systems used in marine exploration tasks [49].

In 2025, the first surface and amphibious unmanned solutions oriented toward practical use in northern and Arctic waters were presented. In July 2025, the cargo amphibious unmanned vehicle "Meridian" was showcased at the international industrial exhibition INNOPROM-2025 [40]. The system, developed with the support of the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia, was at the R&D stage and is designed for payloads of up to 700 kg. Its functional scope includes cargo delivery to hard-to-reach areas, monitoring of land and maritime environments, observation of ice conditions, and participation in search-and-rescue operations. The ability to land on water enables operation in contexts with limited transport infrastructure.

In August 2025, the Murmansk-based company NPK Progress presented a prototype of an uncrewed surface vessel intended for cargo delivery to remote areas of Murmansk Oblast via the Barents Sea [41]. The prototype is designed to carry loads of up to one metric ton. Following completion of trials, the development of a more powerful vessel is planned, indicating an orientation toward stepwise enhancement of technical characteristics in line with regional logistics requirements.

The most institutionally developed direction of maritime unmanned systems in the Arctic has been observed in Arkhangelsk Oblast. In June 2025, at the St. Petersburg International Economic Forum, an agreement was signed between the government of Arkhangelsk Oblast and the companies Sea Project and Uncrewed Logistics on launching a pilot project for the use of maritime unmanned vessels [42], [43]. Arkhangelsk Oblast was designated as the first northern territory in Russia where practical deployment of maritime unmanned systems is planned. The project provides for testing routes between Arkhangelsk and island territories of the Northern Dvina, with subsequent expansion into the White Sea, including the Solovetsky Islands.

The agreement formalizes the role of regional authorities in shaping conditions for the operation of maritime unmanned systems, including the development of roadmaps and a regulatory framework. In particular, by the end of September 2025, preparatory work was planned on the possible introduction of an experimental legal regime in the region for maritime unmanned vessels. According to the Arkhangelsk branch of FSUE Rosmorport, potential launch and recovery points for unmanned vessels have been identified, and the organization of support vessels on a commercial basis is under consideration.

The practical feasibility of the proposed approaches was demonstrated in July 2025 during the first voyage of the uncrewed vessel "Briz" along the Arkhangelsk–Solovetsky Islands route,

with a total distance of approximately 280 km [44]. According to detailed data, around 95% of the route was completed in autonomous mode, with successful testing of obstacle avoidance and safe maneuvering in proximity to other vessels [45]. The experiment confirmed the applicability of maritime unmanned vessels in real navigational conditions in northern waters.

In autumn 2025, the pilot project was characterized as an instrument for testing scenarios of small unmanned vessel use in cargo logistics, identifying technical and organizational constraints, and assessing the economic efficiency of the emerging sector [46]. Project implementation involves the Ministry of Transport of Russia, the government of Arkhangelsk Oblast, Sea Project JSC, and Uncrewed Logistics JSC. The need to develop a dedicated workforce base was also emphasized, including expanded cooperation with regional universities.

In November 2025, the development of maritime unmanned systems was reaffirmed at the federal level. During a working visit to Arkhangelsk, Yuri Trutnev reviewed projects related to maritime unmanned systems and highlighted the need for economic efficiency assessments of such technologies [45]. The potential of uncrewed vessels, including possible defense applications, was also noted. Regional authorities, including Arkhangelsk Oblast Governor Alexander Tsybulsky, linked the development of unmanned technologies to objectives of machinery localization, job creation, and strengthening of the regional economy.

In early 2026, an expansion of the technological base of maritime unmanned systems was recorded through the development of integration tools with aerial platforms. In January 2026, reports emerged on the development of an automated take-off and landing system for unmanned aerial vehicles on board small autonomous vessels [47]. The project is being implemented by the Russian University of Transport in cooperation with the Institute of Control Sciences of the Russian Academy of Sciences under the Priority-2030 program. The system enables automated take-off and landing of UAS from ship decks under conditions of vessel motion, wave-induced roll, and wind loads. It was reported that a prototype system has already been installed on an autonomous vessel and that trials confirmed stable landings under real operating conditions.

For 2026, the launch of two "Briz" uncrewed vessels into operational service in Arkhangelsk Oblast is planned as part of the pilot project. Plans have also been announced for the development of the unmanned vessel "Clipper," designed to carry cargo in a standard 20-foot container. These initiatives reflect a shift toward higher-capacity solutions aimed at integration into existing logistics chains of northern regions.

Overall, technological development of UAS and maritime unmanned systems for Arctic applications in Russia is characterized by a search for integrated solutions encompassing communications, energy systems, autonomy, and resilience to extreme conditions. The developments presented constitute a substantial technological foundation and, in several segments, demonstrate readiness for practical deployment. At the same time, the pace of technological advances often outstrips the formation of stable regimes for operation, access, and maintenance, widening the gap between demonstrated capabilities and regular use. This dynamic directly leads the analysis toward consideration of systemic problems and constraints affecting the further development of unmanned systems in Arctic conditions, including their cross-domain integration across aerial and maritime environments.

6. Practical Limits and System Constraints

The development of the UAS system in the Russian Arctic reveals a set of interrelated problems that reduce the practical feasibility of projects and the effectiveness of public investment.

The first structural constraint concerns deficiencies in system design and in the formulation of technical requirements. A significant number of UAS projects for ice reconnaissance and monitoring are launched with state funding; however, in the absence of an adequate understanding of real operating conditions, use tactics, and system-composition requirements, technically and operationally unviable solutions are produced [2]. This points to systemic errors at the stage of drafting technical specifications and increases the risk of inefficient use of budgetary resources.

A second critical constraint arises from technological challenges in maritime UAS operations. The key barrier to scaling is the unresolved problem of recovery and landing of unmanned aircraft on a moving vessel: vertical landing and parachute-based schemes are unsuitable under Arctic conditions, while automated landing is considered infeasible at the current level of technology. The unresolved issue of UAS recovery thus becomes a systemic limiter for maritime and ice-related use scenarios, regardless of aircraft flight performance.

These technological and design constraints are compounded by the absence of a unified and transparent system for recording actual UAS use in the Arctic. Despite the presence of departmental fleets, pilot projects, and regional initiatives, Russia lacks an integrated data system capable of capturing sortie volumes, use scenarios, incidents, failures, and achieved effects. Fragmented statistics across agencies and regions complicate assessment of solution effectiveness and reduce the manageability of further scaling.

Operational and workforce factors constitute another significant constraint. Alongside active R&D and the demonstration of technological solutions, day-to-day UAS operations under Arctic conditions remain insufficiently developed—covering operator training, organization of maintenance, shift work in remote areas, and allocation of responsibility for autonomous decisions. As a result, a gap emerges between the technical readiness of systems and their regular, safe application in practice.

Additional pressure on the system stems from financial and institutional factors. In 2025, funding for the federal project "Infrastructure Development, Safety Provision, and the Formation of a Specialized UAS Certification System" was reduced by 109 billion rubles (≈ 1.09 billion euros): off-budget sources were fully eliminated (1.9 billion rubles, ≈ 19 million euros), federal allocations were cut from 230.7 to 131 billion rubles (≈ 2.31 to ≈ 1.31 billion euros), and regional funding decreased from 38 to 21.4 billion rubles (≈ 380 to ≈ 214 million euros) [48]. As a result, the project excluded airport equipment for detection and countermeasures against UAS (18.35 billion rubles, ≈ 184 million euros) and significantly reduced the rollout of a unified operator command-and-control infrastructure (from 167 to 105 billion rubles, ≈ 1.67 to ≈ 1.05 billion euros). Only limited measures were retained, including an information system for certification (70 million rubles, ≈ 0.7 million euros) and MPSN stations (40 million rubles, ≈ 0.4 million euros).

This creates a risk of technological asymmetry: in several segments, the development and demonstration of Arctic-capable solutions outpace the formation of stable regimes for access, operation, and accountability. Under these conditions, technically advanced and functional technologies exist, but their systemic deployment is constrained by organizational, workforce, and financial barriers.

As a result, a systemic imbalance emerges: amid unresolved technological and operational bottlenecks in Arctic UAS use, funding for the infrastructure required for safe and scalable deployment is narrowed, limiting the transition from pilot and demonstration projects to a sustainable practice of unmanned system use in the Arctic.

7. Conclusions

In Russian practice, unmanned aerial systems in the Arctic are treated primarily as applied tools for addressing concrete tasks under conditions of limited infrastructure, connectivity, and transport accessibility. The Northern Sea Route remains the key area of application, where UAS are used to enhance navigational and operational safety through more timely and detailed data acquisition. This is complemented by tasks related to environmental monitoring and accident response, logistical support for resource projects and remote settlements, as well as security and emergency response functions.

State policy in the UAS domain during the period under review is structured as centralized and scaling-oriented, without the establishment of a separate "Arctic" project. The Arctic is treated not as an exception but as a priority direction, characterized by specific requirements for regulatory and access mechanisms. The governance logic proceeds from use scenarios to technologies, relying on certification, integration into the unified airspace, support for domestic production, and demand formation through state and departmental procurement.

The resulting regulatory and institutional architecture comprises several interrelated elements. The UAS standards program establishes baseline technical and operational requirements, including operation in low-temperature regimes and remote territories. The integrated airspace use planning system is intended to shift UAS from one-off permits to regular and controlled operation. Experimental legal regimes function as instruments for accelerated deployment where standard regulations do not yet enable practical use, with a trend toward moving from territorial pilots to functional regimes, including the Northern Sea Route. This administrative layer is complemented by the National Drone Adoption Ranking, which is used to compare regions and allocate support measures.

Implementation practice indicates that UAS development in the Arctic is supported not only by policy declarations but also by tangible results. Significant investments in flight management infrastructure have been recorded, alongside tax and financial incentives for manufacturers and the formation of an Arctic infrastructure network comprising testing centers, basing sites, mobile solutions, and adapted aerodromes. UAS application produces measurable effects in resource exploration, monitoring of natural and cryogenic processes, logistics, and environmental safety. The scale of civilian and departmental use is increasing, as evidenced by the existence of dedicated fleets within relevant federal agencies. Technological development is characterized by active R&D and a transition toward integrated solutions aimed at removing key Arctic constraints in communications, energy supply, autonomy, and operational safety, as well as by the development of maritime unmanned systems and their integration with aerial platforms.

The identified problems and constraints significantly affect the viability of this trajectory. Systemic deficiencies persist at the stage of drafting technical specifications, where projects do not fully account for real operating conditions and use tactics. For maritime and ice-related scenarios, a key technological challenge remains unresolved—the recovery and landing of UAS on moving vessels—limiting application regardless of aircraft performance characteristics. A further major constraint is the absence of a unified and transparent accounting system for actual UAS use in the Arctic, as well as insufficiently developed operational requirements and a shortage of trained operators in remote areas. Additional risks arise from financial decisions that reduce funding for certain infrastructure directions, widening the gap between the pace of technological development and the capacity for its practical deployment.

Overall, the analysis indicates that further UAS development in the Russian Arctic is determined less by the availability of individual technologies or pilot projects than by the coherence of design, operations, infrastructure, and governance decisions. Without such coherence, even technically mature solutions risk remaining at the level of demonstrations, whereas its establishment constitutes the key condition for a transition to sustainable and regular unmanned system use in the Arctic.

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